

Kongu Engineering College

[AUTONOMOUS]

PERUNDURAI – 638060.

AUTOMATED COCONUT SHELL CHARCOAL POWDER MAKING MACHINE

BATCH NO: A - 10

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Supervisor

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Estd : 1984

Introduction

The project details the creation of an automated coconut shell charcoal powder machine for efficient, safe, and high-quality production using shredding, carbonization, crushing, screening, and precise automation.

Literature Review

S No	Title of paper	List of Authors	Journal name, Year	Inference
1	Carbonization of Coconut Shell Biomass in a Downdraft Reactor: Effect of Temperature on the Charcoal Properties	Ahmad, R. K., Kamaruddin, M. A., & Abdullah, S. R.	Sains Malaysiana 2021	Higher temperature improves charcoal quality but reduces yields in downdraft reactor carbonization.
2	A Comprehensive Review of Coconut Shell Powder Composites: Preparation, Processing, and Characterization	Ahmad, S. N. I., Ismail, H., Abdullah, C. K., & Bakar, A. A.	Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials 2022	Offers a comprehensive overview of coconut shell powder composites, focusing on preparation, processing, and characterization.

S No	Title of paper	List of Authors	Journal name, Year	Inference
3	Coconut Shell Carbonization Process Using Smokeless Kiln	Arief, R. K., Susilowati, S., & Darmawan, A.	Journal of Applied Agricultural Science and Technology 2023	Discusses a smokeless kiln for coconut shell carbonization, emphasizing an eco-friendly and sustainable approach.
4	Life Cycle Assessment of Activated Carbon Production from Coconut Shells	Arena, N., Zabaniotou, A., & Italiano, C.	Journal of Cleaner Production 2016	Evaluates the environmental impact of producing activated carbon from coconut shells through life cycle assessment.
5	Processing and Utilization of Coconut Wood in Kerala	Anoop, E. V., Kuttappan, R., & Mathew, G.	Journal of the Indian Academy of Wood Science 2011	Explores the processing and utilization of coconut wood in Kerala, aiming to enhance its economic value.

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6	Coconut Shell Pyrolysis for Optimum Charcoal Production	Baygan, G. D., De Luna, M. R., & Bautista, L. T.	Proceedings of International Conference on Technological Challenges for a Better World 2016	Investigates coconut shell pyrolysis for optimal charcoal production.
7	Design of Coconut De-Husker, Cutter and Grater Machine	Bhatia, A., Sharma, R., & Singh, P.	International Journal of Advanced Engineering Research and Applications (IJA-ERA) 2019	Presents the design of machines for processing coconut, improving efficiency.
8	Activated Coconut Shell Charcoal Carbon Using Chemical-Physical Activation	Budi, E., Prasetyo, R., & Santoso, B.	AIP Conference Proceedings 2016	Discusses the production of activated coconut shell charcoal through chemical-physical activation methods.

S No	Title of paper	List of Authors	Journal name, Year	Inference
9	Low-Tech Coconut Shell Activated Charcoal Production	Cobb, A., & Clarkson, P. J.	International Journal for Service Learning in Engineering, Humanitarian Engineering and Social Entrepreneurship 2012	Highlights a low-tech approach to producing activated charcoal from coconut shells.
10	Calorific Value Variation in Coconut Stem Wood	Dhamodaran, T. K., Kumar, P., & Thomas, E.	Wood Science and Technology 1989	Examines variations in the calorific value of coconut stem wood.
11	Yield and Quality of Charcoal from Coconut Stem Wood	Gnanaharan, R., Ramesh, M. V., & Kumar, C. S.	Biomass 1988	Evaluates the yield and quality of charcoal produced from coconut stem wood.

S No	Title of paper	List of Authors	Journal name, Year	Inference
12	Oxidative Bleaching of Coconut Charcoal Polyester Fiber	Gundogan, M., & Akyuz, M.	TEXTILE SCIENCE AND ECONOMY 2020	Explores the oxidative bleaching of coconut charcoal polyester fiber.
13	An Experimental Study of Liquid Smoke and Charcoal Production from Coconut Shell	Hasan, H., Ismail, H., & Abdullah, C. K.	Journal of Physics: Conference Series 2022	Investigates liquid smoke and charcoal production from coconut shells using indirect burning.
14	Development of Coconut Dehusker Machine for a Small-Scale Industry	Herdian, F., Hardiansyah, S., & Suryana, A.	Journal of Applied Agricultural Science and Technology 2019	Focuses on designing a coconut dehusker machine suitable for small-scale industries.

S No	Title of paper	List of Authors	Journal name, Year	Inference
15	An Automatic Trimming Machine for Young Coconut Fruit	Jarimopas, B., Lekcharoensuk, C., & Kasetsart, J.	Biosystems Engineering 2009	Describes an automatic trimming machine for young coconut fruits.
16	Designing of a Coconut Chopping Machine and Making Fuel from Tender Coconut	Koteswararao, B., Sreenivasa Rao, K., & Rajasekhar, K.	Indian J Sci Technol 2016	Presents a coconut chopping machine and fuel production from tender coconuts.
17	Burner Characteristics for Activated Carbon Production	Leman, A. M., Abdullah, S. N. H., & Mohamad, M. F.	MATEC Web of Conferences 2017	Investigates burner characteristics for activated carbon production.
18	Design and Development of Automated Coconut Dehusking and Crown Removal Machine	Sa, V., & Venkataramanan, K.	International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology 2023	Focuses on designing an automated machine for coconut dehusking and crown removal.

S No	Title of paper	List of Authors	Journal name, Year	Inference
19	Regression Modeling and Residual Analysis of Screening Coal in a Screening Machine	Shanmugam, B. K., & Rajesh, N.	International Journal of Coal Preparation and Utilization 2022	Utilizes regression modeling and residual analysis for screening coal in a machine.
20	Porous Silica and Carbon-Derived Materials from Rice Husk Pyrolysis Char	Shen, Y., Wang, S., Tang, J., & Sun, L.	Microporous and Mesoporous Materials 2014	Discusses porous silica and carbon-derived materials from rice husk pyrolysis char.
21	Mechanical Properties of Reinforced Epoxy Composite Using Waste Coconut Shell Charcoal	Sindhu, P., Bindu, R., & Sreekala, M. S.	International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology 2018	Explores mechanical properties of epoxy composites with waste coconut shell charcoal reinforcement.

S No	Title of paper	List of Authors	Journal name, Year	Inference
22	Design and Fabrication of Automated Biomass Briquetting Machine	Solanki, S., & Patel, R.	International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology 2022	Focuses on designing and fabricating an automated biomass briquetting machine.
23	Use of Eco-Benign Periwinkle Shell Particle for Making Composites	Valsadwala, A. S., Bhatt, J. H., & Patel, D. H.	Journal of Polymers and the Environment 2022	Utilizes eco-benign periwinkle shell particles for making composites and studying their thermal and mechanical effects.
24	Design and Development of Young Coconut Shaving Machine	Yahya, S., & Mohamad, M. F.	International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology 2019	Focuses on designing a machine for young coconut shaving.

Summary of Literature

- Literature: Sustainable resource management and technology.
- Research: Creating valuable materials from agricultural by-products.
- Advancements: Reducing environmental impact and improving waste management.
- Machinery: Efficient agricultural waste utilization and growth opportunities.

Problem Identified from an Industry

- Slaggy production rate
- Huge health risk factors for working people
- In India there is about few Industries who produce coconut shell charcoal powder

29th March 2023.

From,

Dilip Vijay Ram A [20MTR015],
III – Year,
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Tamil Nadu, India.

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To,

The proprietor,
VESP Energy,
41-Ramananda Nagar,
Saravanampatti,
Coimbatore – 641035,
Tamil Nadu, India.

Contact: +91 9952263407
Email ID: vespenergy@gmail.com

Dear Sir / Mam,

Subject: Reg. Requisition letter of Factory visit for project development.

I'm here to let you know that myself along with my teammate **Aswin S** and **Durai prem G**, are working under a Design and fabrication project on "Coconut shell charcoal briquette manufacturing process" under the guidance of **Dr. R. Parameshwaran** [Professor - Department of Mechatronics Engineering, Chief Coordinator (TBI & Placement Training)]. So, we need an onsite exposure to analyse the entire work process for the development of our project. Kindly grant us permission to visit your firm on **05.04.2023 (Wednesday)**.

S.no	Name	Roll number	Signature
1.	ASWIN S	20MTL098	
2.	DILIPVIJAY RAM A	20MTR015	
3.	DURAI PREM G	20MTR017	

Dr. R. Parameshwaran
(Project Guide)

Dr. B. Meenakshipriya
(HOD, Mechatronics Engineering)

Risk factors of Manual - charcoal Powder Making Process

Objective

The goal is to develop a low-cost automated machine for coconut tree farmers to produce a value-added product, charcoal powder from coconut shells, by enhancing efficiency, quality, and worker safety.

Flow chart of powder charcoal processing

Estd : 1984

Computer Aided – Design Model of charcoal powder processing

Estd : 1984

SHREDDER

Stage -1:

Shredding the dried coconuthusks into finite fibers.

Design Calculation [Shredder]

Desired output = **40Kgs / 40L**

Avg. Weight of 1 coconut shell = **500gms**

For 1Kg of output = **2 coconut shells**

For 40Kgs of output = **80 coconut shells**

Based on the Hopper dimension its possible to **feed 3 coconut shells per batch**

Thus, Per batch needs = **2 seconds to shred**

Number of batches = Total no. of coconut shells / 3 = **26 batch**

Total time for the process: $26 \times 2 =$ **52 Seconds**

Approx time: 60 seconds

FURNACE

Stage - 2:

Carbonizing the dried coconut husk fibers.

Flippers

FURNACE

Stage - 2:

Carbonizing the dried coconut husk fibers.

Tapered runway

Design Calculation [Furnace]

Volume of cylinder = $\pi \times R^2 \times H$

Radius (R) = 901.93 mm

Height (H) = 264.18 mm

Volume of Cylinder = **60,000,000mm³**

In terms of Litres = **60L**

In terms of Kgs = **60Kgs**

Scientific calculation = **40Kgs will produce 15Kgs of output**

CRUSHER & SCREENER

Stage - 3:

Two in one machine where both crushing and screening process takes place.

Design Calculation [Crusher & Screener]

Motor Specification:

Speed = 900 rpm

Type = Induction motor

Power source = AC

Calculation:

15Kgs of Output produced from Furnace will undergo crushing process and further it will be screened and produce an **Approx. output of 10Kgs**

Estd : 1984

Ladder Logic circuit

Shredder

→ Hopper

→ V Belt

→ Relay

→ Single phase Induction motor

Furnace

Hopper

Furnace chamber

Burner

Transmission hose

Solenoid Valve

Screener

→ Twin shaft crusher

→ Screener

→ V Belt

→ Single phase Induction motor

→ Relay

Components Used

- Siemens S7-1200 PLC
- Single phase induction Motor(1440 RPM)
- Solenoid valve
- Nozzle
- Fuel Reservoir
- Powder butterfly valve
- Electric lighter
- Single phase induction Motor (900 RPM)
- V Belt
- Relay
- Gas tube

Estd : 1984

Process Outcome

- An automated coconut shell charcoal powder making machine.
- Efficient conversion of coconut shells into high-quality charcoal powder.
- Mechanical processes include shredding, carbonizing, crushing, and screening.
- Components: shredder, furnace, twin shaft crusher & screener, and control system.
- Minimal manual intervention and smooth operation.
- Smaller fragments for better carbonization.
- Fine charcoal powder suitable for various applications.
- Precise control of machine parameters through the control system.

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Estd : 1984

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Thank
you!